

Typology of citizen participation (around energy)

Deliverable WP1-D3

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About the EnergyPOLITIES Project

EnergyPOLITIES aims to develop an in-depth understanding of citizen participation in the energy transition, the socio-economic and socio-cultural factors which shape it, and the intersections between these and the governance frameworks within which decisions are made. This involves an initial mapping of current patterns of citizen engagement with the energy system, from active consumers to social mobilisation, and from political campaigners to members of community energy projects.

This mapping forms the basis of a typology of citizen participation, which links specific participation forms to the governance structures which condition them and the socio-demographic characteristics of citizens. This typology will subsequently be applied in an in-depth analysis of three case studies of energy projects (two Irish and one mainland EU) that have stimulated significant citizen participation. Integrating both quantitative and qualitative methods, the case studies will reveal linkages between political, institutional and organisational frameworks and citizen participation in the energy system.

EnergyPOLITIES will explore how governance structures intersect with the socio-economic and key socio-cultural factors, including gender, to influence the social acceptability or otherwise of energy infrastructure projects. The business models deployed in each project will be analysed from the perspective of their impact on inclusiveness, gender, democracy and social acceptability; stakeholders' perceptions of distributional and procedural justice will be explored. Recommendations will be developed for how multi-level governance structures, and business models can support inclusive citizen participation and thereby enhance the social acceptability of the energy transition.

For more information see <https://www.ucc.ie/en/energypolities/>

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is the last of three reports from work package 1 '*Mapping of participation in the energy system*', which focuses on understanding citizen participation at various levels within the system, and how these are influenced by current and emerging governance structures. The topics explored in this report build upon those investigated as part of the first and second deliverables, namely how citizens participate as consumers, as citizens and as communitarians, and how these identities are shaped by emerging governance and organisational frameworks. This report outlines a number of modes of participation typically seen within the energy system, and investigates how potential energy futures may be shaped by – and will themselves determine – the nature of citizen participation with the energy system. This research will provide a solid foundation to the work carried out as part of later work packages which will examine citizen participation in a number of case studies.

1 Introduction

1.1 Context

The EnergyPolities project is centred around uncovering a rich understanding of the significant aspects of citizen participation within the energy transition. The approach taken has focused on examining the complex and overlapping relationships observable between the governance frameworks, socio-economic and socio-cultural factors that impact the engagement of citizens with the energy system.

The following report draws together a typology of citizen participation with the energy system, which will feed into research to be carried out on the three case studies at the centre of this project, namely:

- The Corrib Gas Project, in Co. Mayo, Ireland: the development of a gas field and construction of a natural gas pipeline and processing plant.
- The Grid Link Project in eastern and southern Ireland: a proposal by EirGrid to install a fully overhead 400k HVAC line aimed at bettering the transmission infrastructure throughout the country.
- The Ternitz Project in lower Austria: a partnership between a local municipality and industry and individual citizens which saw the development of the city's first citizen solar power project.

Work Package 1 of the EnergyPolities project aims to examine citizen participation at a number of different levels, mapping participation in the energy system and investigating how this participation is shaped by emerging governance and organisational frameworks. This research will culminate in the development of a typology of citizen participation within energy systems. The primary objectives of this work package are outlined in Box 1 below.

1. Understand and classify citizen participation in energy system as consumers, as citizens and as communitarians.
2. Undertake a comprehensive mapping of existing patterns of participation in the energy system of energy consumers, energy citizens and energy communitarians.
3. Develop a better understanding of how these patterns of energy participation intersects with the organisation and functioning of, and governance in, the energy system.

Box 1: Objectives of EnergyPolities Work Package 1 'Mapping of participation in the energy system'

This deliverable, '*Typology of citizen participation*', is grounded in the work carried out as part of WP1's first two deliverables: '*Report on citizen participation at the macro level*' and '*Description of emergent governance & organisational frameworks*'. These provide the foundation in consumerist,

civic and communitarian forms of participation necessary to explore, in this typology, the various ways that citizens engage with the energy system and how their actions are conditioned by current and emerging governance structures.

1.2 Background

Achieving a successful clean energy transition will require societal acceptance and buy-in for the many changes required in the way we produce and use energy, and more generally in the way we live our lives. This acceptance has, to date, not been achieved, as demonstrated by the strong public opposition encountered by energy projects, which threatens to significantly slow down Europe's energy transition (Cohen *et al.*, 2014; Enevoldsen & Sovacool, 2016). A 'social gap' has emerged between support for renewable energies (and other projects required for the clean energy transition) in principle and local opposition to such energy projects (González *et al.*, 2016). The feeling of exclusion from the decision-making process, aggravated by the fact that benefits are seen to be accrued by others, can lead to substantial opposition to such projects. The centralised and market-driven character of much energy infrastructure and renewable energy planning and development does not facilitate or encourage the participation of individual citizens or local communities. To address this challenge, and to overcome what some would describe as alienation of the public from the policy sector, governments increasingly stress the importance of greater public participation on energy – with the subtext being that this would lead to greater acceptance of projects related to the clean energy transition.

However, the nature and depth of desirable citizen participation in the energy system is perhaps best described as contested – with the associated discourse often marked by contradiction and paradox. In an earlier output from this project¹, six expressions of citizen participation in the energy system were identified:

- A traditional **consumption-based role**, wherein a citizen's only 'permitted' role in the energy system was that of a passive and receptive customer – *Passive consumer*;
- An active **market-based role**, where the consumer is encouraged to use their purchasing power to send signals to suppliers and thereby influence the market – *Active consumer*;
- An **information-based role**, where appropriately informed and educated, consumers are expected to act as good citizens by doing the right thing (as defined by those in power) – *Good citizen*;

¹ WP1-D1 Citizen Participation in the Energy System at the Macro Level

- **Rights-based participation**, which relies on legalistic definitions of rights and interpretation of law in responding to proposed policy changes or energy projects – *Constitutionalist*;
- **Production-based participation**, moving beyond the expected participation as consumers to see citizens become involved in energy projects both individually² and collectively³ – *Producer*;
- **Politics-based participation**, with citizens arguing and organising in support of different perspectives on energy in national and European public arenas – *Challenger*.

Furthermore, the report suggested it was perhaps useful to consider these roles not as strictly demarcated categories, but rather as particular expressions of how people might engage with the energy system⁴, acknowledging that people can play different, and sometimes concurrent, roles depending on the circumstances at a particular point in time. The nature of the public participation in the energy system is to a large extent dependent on the roles that people are permitted to play by rules and norms which combine to structure the energy system. These rules and norms – the governance frameworks around the energy system along with organisational choices made on configuring energy projects influence (and at times direct) public involvement with, and participation in, the energy system. This includes, but is not limited to shaping such things as:

- Potential means of citizens, individually and/or collectively, contributing to energy policy deliberations;
- The nature of how citizen and communities are permitted to input into energy project planning and consent processes;
- The scope and oversight of community benefit schemes associated with energy projects;
- Opportunities for citizens to have direct economic involvement in local energy projects;
- Access to compensation for citizens and communities impacted by energy infrastructure;
- Regulatory facilitation and support of community-based energy projects.

This report aims to explore how these rules, norms and organisational arrangements are established. This is key to appreciating how and why citizens adopt particular roles in the energy system, and

² Either as prosumers (someone who both produces and consumes energy) or as shareholders in energy producing companies

³ Combined together with others to realise community energy projects

⁴ In WP1-D2, the term ‘energy citizenship’ was used (in a basic understanding) to signify the means by which a citizen-consumer chooses to engage with the energy system.

importantly understanding what changes in these structural contexts might mean for the evolution of such participation.

1.3 Structure of the document

This deliverable is divided into five sections as outlined below:

1 – Introduction, describing the foundation of the project and giving background and context to the research outlined in this report.

2 – Methodology, presenting a review of the literature relating to citizen participation within the energy system.

3 – Overview of WP1-D1 Citizen Participation, detailing the various modes of participation of citizens in the energy system.

4 – Discussion, illustrating the key findings of the research, including outlining a number of potential energy futures and the types of citizen engagement these promote.

5 – Conclusions, summarizing the report's key findings and clarifying how these fit into and support the EnergyPolities project as a whole.

2 Methodology

2.1 Literature Review

Literature reviews – though oftentimes considered a precursor to ‘real’ research – are a vital part of the research process (Onwuegbuzie & Freis, 2016). The method is frequently used as a means of framing subsequent research to be undertaken, though is also considered a research method in its own right which enables the synthesis and integration of existing knowledge from the literature into a form that produces new knowledge and insights (Torraco, 2005). The objectives of this literature review were to develop an understanding of manners through which citizens engage with the energy system, and ultimately support the development of a typology of citizen participation.

A combination of commercial databases (available through university subscriptions) and freely accessible databases (Science Direct, JSTOR and Google Scholar) were used as part of the literature search. Keyword search constructions – comprising words, phrases and basic Boolean operators – were created for the database searches; Boolean search combinations encourage flexibility and precision within database searches. The methodology also used a ‘backward’ and ‘forward’ snowballing strategy to locate more relevant literature.

The resultant list of literature was screened to ensure that the papers were usable, meaning that *‘they cover the topic of interest, are in a language you can read, and are in a publication you respect and can be obtained in a timely manner.’* (Fink, 2010, p. 59). This literature then underwent a further methodological screening (*i.e.*, looking at the quality of the work and the journal, the author’s reputation, *etc.*) to ensure suitability. Consideration of such attributes tends to result in a higher quality and more focused literature review.

The list of literature gathered was subsequently screened for usability. ‘Usable’ here means that *‘they cover the topic of interest, are in a language you can read, and are in a publication you respect and can be obtained in a timely manner.’* (Fink, 2010, p. 59). A further methodological screening was then undertaken on the literature, involving a careful examination of the quality of the work, the journal, the reputation of the author, *etc.* so to ensure suitability and result in a literature that is more clearly focused and of higher quality.

The details of the literature gathered were input into a reference management software; the use of a cite-as-you-write plug-in for word processing when using a database of references enables a more user-friendly experience of reading, notetaking and organising documents. The review of the literature followed the iterative processes of searching, reading, annotating, organising, summarising, analysing and, lastly, synthesising.

2.2 Data Analysis and Interpretation

Qualitative data, like interview notes, may be analysed with the goal of characterising and explaining social phenomena (Pope *et al.*, 2000). Rich understandings may be gleaned from this recursive, laborious and time-consuming process. Data analysis of each interview from the case studies began with an examination of the extensive notes taken during the discussion, repeated until the material became familiar to the analyst. Key information and themes relevant to energy justice and social acceptance of energy projects were identified through a line-by-line analysis of the text. This exercise began with the cross-referencing of information with that gathered from academic literature and publicly available documentation with the aim of filling gaps in knowledge, resolving inconsistencies and pointing out any additional information needs. This exercise was followed by a standard thematic analysis of the text in which it was systematically ordered, categorised and labelled in a process known as coding. In this process identifying codes are applied to relevant sections of text, sometimes using a qualitative data analysis software like NVivo, to code, organise, link and cross-reference material. The iterative analysis and interpretation process was significantly abbreviated by this practice. The researchers involved in the analyses coordinated their activities and jointly reviewed their work.

3 Citizen participation around energy

3.1 Introduction

The EnergyPolities project aspires to develop a deeper insight into the realm of citizen participation in the energy transition, including the socio-economic and socio-cultural factors that condition these engagements and their interactions with various governance frameworks. The first deliverable, 'Citizen Participation in the Energy System at the Macro Level', provided a necessary introduction to citizen participation in the energy transition. The report was based upon desk research which explored the manners in which citizens participate in the energy system, showing particular concern to the ways citizens would like to participate, and the ways they are allowed to. The report formed the foundation for subsequent research as part of WP1 on emergent governance and organisation frameworks and the realisation of this typology of citizen participation.

3.2 Civic Participation

Effective citizen participation, referring to the involvement of citizens in public decision-making processes, is an entirely different form of governance (Baum, 2001). Participation, in this context, encompasses practices ranging from simple observation to the application of social and economic power, a term expanded over the years to encompass a number of citizen-oriented, social action initiatives led by the government. Proponents of citizen participation in the energy arena emphasise

the potential it holds for empowering individuals and communities, though inherent difficulties have long been acknowledged (E. M. Burke, 1968) with citizen participation, particularly as tensions rise between participatory democracy and professional expertise. Participation has generally been described in terms of four main categories:

- *Active Consumerism*: Consumerism can be characterised as citizens participating in the market as consumers, in so far as they are able to choose one product or service over another. Consumerist principles have been re-evaluated in recent years and discussed in terms of their passivity and activity depending on the motivations and behaviours of these consumers. The rollout of smart technologies has brought this form of participation to the fore as consumers are positioned in more proactive roles as both innovators and co-producers of energy (Fox *et al.*, 2017). There is increasing recognition that the passive and active consumer is a construct created by energy actors intent on maintaining the status quo.
- *Prosumerism*: The term ‘prosumer’, coined by Toffler (1980) in the book ‘*The Third Wave*’, refers to citizens who are able to produce at least some of the goods and services they use for their own consumption. Toffler theorised that the majority of people could either be classified as prosumers or consumers. The number of prosumers is on the rise within the energy system, evidenced by the increasing deployment of domestic solar (and to a lesser extent wind) energy installations. This is related to, and to a degree will be enhanced by, the adopt of electric vehicles.
- *Communitarianism*: Communitarianism is described by Mullally, Dunphy and O’Connor (2018) as ‘*citizenship anchored in community membership*’. Communitarian philosophers (MacIntyre, 1988; Taylor, 1989) have emphasised the importance community has in shaping society and influencing the actions and behaviours of individuals. Energy communitarianism involves collective actions in the energy sphere exemplified by energy co-operatives (which are being so prevalent, that for some energy citizenship is almost synonymous with energy co-operative membership).
- *Participatory Citizenship*: Participatory citizenship is an integral part of democracy. The overall quality, robustness and good health of the democratic traditions of a country may be observed through changes in levels of citizen participation within the processes of democratic decision-making. The meaning of the term ‘participation’ remains somewhat vague or even contradictory, which has led to mixed outcomes for aspects of the energy transition *e.g.*, the ‘social gap’ observed in renewable energy siting decisions.

The discourse on citizen participation with the energy system has resulted in increased focus on concepts such as energy justice, democracy and citizenship. Energy justice relates to one of the most significant challenges to the energy system – feelings of unfairness. Energy justice may be conceptualised as involving three dimensions: distributional (relating to the distribution of costs and benefits), procedural (relating to the fairness of decision-making processes) and recognitive (relating to the inclusion of all groups of society). Energy democracy refers to the conceptualisation of a fairer, more inclusive and democratic energy system which establishes the energy transition as more than just the substitution of one set of energy sources for another. Energy democracy is made up of numerous elements identified by Szulecki (2018) as including increased participation in decision-making processes and public/community ownership of energy production, as well as increased social benefits in terms of employment, quality of life and sustainability. Lastly, energy citizenship relates to an exploration of the role that citizens could and should be allowed to play in the energy transition. This concept conceives the citizen as an active participant in the energy system, though, as Mullally, Dunphy and O'Connor (2018) point out, the type of 'energy citizens' these participants are invited to be remains quite unclear.

3.3 Modes of Energy Participation

The importance of public participation in the energy system for contributing towards a fairer and more democratic energy transition has garnered great recognition in recent years. The concept of energy citizenship has emerged from this discourse, relating to the role that citizens could (or should) be allowed to play as part of this energy transition. The six main modes of participation identified as part of this report are discussed below.

3.3.1 THE PASSIVE CONSUMER – CONSUMPTION-BASED ROLE

This traditional consumption-based role frames the citizen as a passive consumer of energy and has represented the long-held, traditional view of the citizen in the energy domain. This role symbolises a transactional relationship between a 'fortunate recipient' and a benevolent energy industry whereby a marvellous commodity is sold to passive consumers in return for money. In this scenario, the energy system is influenced, and policies directed, by experts, while citizens were solely permitted to act as customers of the system. As time has progressed, there has been a growing acceptance of a diverse range of alternative roles for citizens in the energy sphere, some of which are outlined below. Both the passive and active consumer (see below) roles follow the consumerist narrative, which frames energy citizenship solely in terms of people's role as consumers and assumes that their input of any should be through influencing the energy system through decentralised, often domestic choices, despite taking place within a centralised agenda-setting and policy process (Mullally *et al.*, 2018).

3.3.2 THE ACTIVE CONSUMER – MARKET-BASED ROLE

The market-based representation of citizens within the energy sphere sees them framed as ‘active’ consumers who may exert influence over the system through their purchasing power. The active consumer is said to be empowered by existing transactional rights and responsibilities. From this perspective, systemic change is possible through the collective actions of multiple individual consumers making ‘smart choices’ to send signals to energy companies which will subsequently bring about change in the market. Researchers often express criticism of this portrayal for its ignorance of the limited nature of choices actually offered to the ‘active’ consumer with regard to energy, which usually sees the citizen simply selecting one product or service over another. It is rare that the citizen is allowed to participate in the planning and development phases of products, services or parts of the energy system itself. Thus, despite receiving the label of ‘active’ consumer, this role remains quite passive with respect to their engagement with the energy system.

3.3.3 THE GOOD CITIZEN – INFORMATION-BASED ROLE

The concept of the ‘good citizen’ in the energy domain is where citizens act in the greater good, however that may be defined. It emerged first in response to the energy crises of the 1970s, and more recently in response to the climate crisis, it accompanies the paternalist’s discourse coalition on citizen participation in the energy system as described by Mullally *et al.* (2018). This concept is based on an information-deficit model which sees the citizen depicted as someone who is simply ill-informed and therefore needs to be educated and persuaded to do the ‘right thing’ and make the ‘right’ choices (Lennon *et al.*, 2020). This form of participation sees government and industry elites continuing to control the energy system from the top-down, a system which is favoured by those that prefer minimum disruption by citizens. This framing represents the transfer of responsibility from those with power and resources to individual citizens, without acknowledging the systemic challenges faced by citizens which contribute to their lack of power and resources necessary to instigate change. Proponents of this information-based role naively expects citizens to deliver in spite of a highly-centralised and limiting pathway for participation. Moreover, it places many of the moral responsibilities for realising the energy transition on their shoulders yet the system remains controlled by legally-mandated processes established by the elites who are incentivised to resist change to the existing status quo (participation characterised by commodity-oriented, transactional engagements). This form of energy citizenship results in no change to the institutional status quo, and thus, no role for the average citizen beyond acquiescence and changing their behaviour in order to align with the policies set out by government (Mullally *et al.*, 2018). While this engagement method is not deliberative, it is also not illegitimate, and some citizens may not necessarily be adverse to this form of engagement, in which responsibility for energy is delegated to someone else.

3.3.4 THE CONSTITUTIONALIST – RIGHTS-BASED PARTICIPATION

The, which

Mullally *et al.* (2018), identify the ‘constitutionalist’ as the main protagonist of this rights-based approach to citizen participation. Similar to the market- and information-based approaches, this form of participation focuses on maintaining pre-existing socio-technical structures, in that constitutionalists show concern for their rights and the interpretation of the law, initiating non-disruptive changes to existing legal arrangements. This method of engagement is popular amongst communities and protest groups looking to challenge a proposed infrastructural development in their locality, often involving the groups exercising existing legal rights in order to establish themselves in terms of a consent/dissent dichotomy. This form of participation typically represents the last resort for citizens to participate in a project due to lack of engagement by the project promoter during the early stages of the development. In this scenario, decision-making powers rest with the practitioners of legal frameworks, rather than with citizens.

3.3.5 THE PRODUCER – PRODUCTION-BASED PARTICIPATION

Citizens as producers of energy has become a source of excitement in recent times, as efforts to decarbonise the energy system have facilitated and somewhat encouraged movement away from the dominant narrative of citizens as consumers. This movement has manifested itself in a number of ways, including microgeneration ‘prosumption’ of energy, investments in energy production projects and the formation of energy cooperatives (EESC, 2016). Deliberative discourses emphasise this constructive and active role for energy citizens in shaping the energy system, however this mode of participation has become mainstreamed in such a way that community energy initiatives are often associated with energy citizen participation, and an over-emphasis is placed on the potential of this form of participation. Despite its potential, becoming a citizen-producer is generally only a possibility for those with sufficient economic and social privilege and it remains that existing modes of development are favoured in place of more disruptive approaches to participation, which are discouraged. Similar to the concept of the ‘good citizen’, the promotion of prosumption tends to shift the responsibility for creating a more sustainable energy system on to citizens and takes the onus away from the energy industry to increase the pace of their decarbonisation efforts. Unsurprisingly, production-based participation is therefore favoured by those who prefer minimal changes.

3.3.6 THE CHALLENGER – POLITICS-BASED PARTICIPATION

Politics-based participation occurs where citizens attempt to influence the energy system through engaging in public debate in national and European public arenas. This form of participation is characteristic of strongly-motivated citizens who desire to challenge the status quo, driven by a

diverse range of issues at both the local and global scales. Typical examples of this form of engagement include demonstrations of opposition to wind farms (Cass & Walker, 2009); expressions of concern about climate change (Bowman, 2019); anger over energy prices; and calls for increased deployment of renewable technologies (Hager, 2015). This form of participation exists along a spectrum of activity, depending on the circumstances and experiences of those involved, ranging from formal participation in the decision-making process to local actions taken by groups protesting energy infrastructure developments. This politics-based participation can prove most challenging to the status quo as it contests the very basis of decision-making around the energy system, opening up the range of decisions to be made. It has the potential to disrupt existing energy configurations, thus offering the chance of significant social innovation.

3.3.7 SUMMATION

The WP1-D1 Citizen Participation deliverable focused on developing a deeper understanding of the different modes of citizen participation emerging around energy. Informed by related work (Dunphy *et al.*, 2017; Lennon *et al.*, 2019, 2020; Mullally *et al.*, 2018), the report explored examples from the literature of existing and emerging modes of participation, identifying a number of roles played by citizens within the energy system. Escobar (2017)'s work on the kind of citizen that citizens are invited to be formed a solid foundation for the deliverable, describing citizen participation through the lenses of representative, participatory and deliberative democracy. In his paper on 'Pluralism and Democratic Participation' Escobar describes how representative democracy, in which the role of citizens is minimalist, appears to be the most widespread and 'workable form of democracy' given the complexities of governance and policymaking (Elstub & McLaverty, 2014). In this instance citizens are invited to be voters or spectators who leave political action to the elite individuals or interest groups they elect. This form of democracy aligns with the paternalist, majoritarian and consumerist constructions of energy citizens described by Mullally *et al.* (2018) which aim to activate citizens within a centralised, top-down model in ways that conform to objectives set by policy-makers. Conversely, in the case of participatory democracy citizens are invited to play a very different role in that they are encouraged to engage with each other without intermediaries, thus creating a political arena which is based upon ongoing citizen participation in planning, coordinating and enacting collective futures (Barber, 2003). Deliberative democracy represents an enhanced form of participatory democracy in which communication, rather than voting, remains the key means of citizen participation and citizens are invited to be considered deliberators in discussions on policy (Escobar, 2017). Both of these forms of democracy are more closely aligned with the constitutionalists, communitarians and deliberative democrats' construct of energy citizenship in which participation takes place in a number of ways that encourage the creation of a more bottom-up model of energy governance.

4 Towards a typology

4.1 Introduction

The complex set of challenges that climate change presents has led governments across the world to set ambitious renewable energy targets to be achieved by specific dates in future. The evolution of electricity over the course of the last century has resulted in energy systems characterised by large-scale generation, centralised transmission and distribution and small numbers of state-owned operators or investors acting as the key players owning and operating the energy systems. The integration of local renewable energy technologies into the current energy system will therefore bring about changes in the physical and organisational infrastructure of the energy system, and will require comprehensive planning, organisation and cooperation between policy makers, consumers and communities, and utilities. This realisation has seen the rolling out of policy instruments that mainly take advantage of price mechanisms in order to deploy sustainable energy, offering little consideration to concerns around energy justice such as *who* owns the energy system, *what* technologies are deployed and *how* the energy produced is used (Grant *et al.*, 2018; Gunderson, Stuart & Petersen, 2018; Gunderson, Stuart, Petersen & Yun 2018; Healy & Barry, 2017; Jenkins *et al.*, 2016, 2018; Jorgenson *et al.*, 2018; Lawhon & Murphy, 2012; Newell & Mulvaney, 2013; Thombs, 2018b). Various sustainable energy narratives have sprung forth from this debate, and have resulted in the development of a number of typologies of citizen engagement with the energy system which ultimately strive to identify opportunities for growth and the achievement of energy justice.

4.2 Potential Energy Futures

The just transition and scholar-activist energy democracy literatures view energy technologies as processes embedded within larger socio-ecological systems and argue that the scale of energy technologies and systems play a critical role in the facilitation of just and democratic futures. This discourse led Thombs (2019) to devise a typology based upon the issues of social power and energy system scale as a means of exploring how potential energy futures might be envisioned, as well as the key factors that will drive and shape these futures. The concept of 'just transitions' and the issues of power and justice related to energy futures have recently been explored by scholars who argue that structural changes are necessary for addressing the climate change crisis and creating a more sustainable future (M. J. Burke & Stephens, 2018; Farrell, 2011; Grant *et al.*, 2018; Gunderson, Stuart, & Petersen, 2018; Gunderson, Stuart, Petersen & Yun 2018; Healy & Barry, 2017; Jenkins *et al.*, 2016, 2018; Jorgenson *et al.*, 2018; Lawhon & Murphy, 2012; Newell & Mulvaney, 2013; Sovacool *et al.*, 2016; Sovacool & Dworkin, 2015; Thombs, 2018a; Thombs, 2018b; Weinrub & Giancattarino, 2015). Energy itself is considered to be intertwined with many social processes, embedded within social structures and systems of social power – the discussion of energy futures therefore requires

simultaneous debate on social structures, the scale of energy systems and technologies employed as part of them.

In his typology, Thombs (2019) argues that energy futures may be determined in part by the interaction of a social scale, organised on a spectrum of democratic to monopolistic, with an energy system scale, on a spectrum of centralised to decentralised. This typology sees potential energy futures fall into four broad quadrants of a 2 x 2 matrix which includes (1) libertarian energy decentralism; (2) technocratic energy centralism; (3) democratic energy centralism; and (4) democratic energy decentralism (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The four potential energy futures envisioned by Thombs (2019).

The x-axis is defined as a dichotomy falling along a spectrum ranging from democratic to monopolistic. Thombs (2019) conceives democracy according to the guiding principle of ‘one person, one vote’ that allows communities to decide upon matters relating to energy for themselves; in contrast, ‘monopolistic’ processes typifying a society in which control over social structures and decision-making processes are held by a few elite individuals. Similarly, the y-axis consists of a spectrum ranging from centralised to decentralised. A centralised system refers to energy activities (generation, transmission and distribution) which occur at an aggregate level and where production of energy is separated from end-use. A decentralised system, on the other hand, involves aspects of the system which are concentrated at micro levels, with production and consumption occurring within relatively close proximity. Scale is important to this typology – while decentralisation remains relatively fixed and is more straight-forward in many aspects, centralised systems may vary in scale depending on the particular context.

The bottom righthand quadrant in the typology described by Thombs (2019) is labelled 'libertarian energy decentralism', defined by a monopolistic and decentralised future. In this scenario the economic, political and civil realms of society and the energy system are controlled by a small number of elites who are concerned with making profits from distributed energy technologies. Government oversight and regulation is minimal in this scenario. Energy tends to be regarded as a private good, something that citizens cannot access unless they have the money to purchase it as an end-user. The ideal scenario envisioned here is a group of elite prosumers who could afford distributed energy and storage technologies and thus become independent from the energy system, establishing self-sufficient homes, buildings and companies. This future is a reality in some US states like Nevada and Florida where utility companies are seen as a wasteful middleman and distributed technologies as an opportunity to create new markets within which individuals who are able to afford these technologies sell energy to those who cannot. Environmental and economic justice concerns are paid little attention in this scenario, with those who cannot afford such technologies becoming reliant on a crumbling central grid system, forced to purchase energy from the rich, or left without access to energy resources altogether.

Technocratic energy centralism, described by the top right-hand quadrant, consists of societies characterised by centralised energy systems which are controlled in a monopolistic fashion, a future similar to many present-day societies. Corporations, government regulatory bodies and utility companies control the decision-making process in this scenario, which is characterised by a few elite actors - private monopolies or state-owned institutions with little accountability to the general public – who hold all the power. This future would likely see the replacement of fossil fuels with renewable energy technologies, but the grid infrastructure would remain centralised, and vulnerable populations would receive little assistance and resources to purchase energy. This future is already observable in New York State where the Reforming the Energy Vision initiative has largely sought to promote the deployment of large-scale renewables while maintaining, albeit reshaping slightly, the general structure of the current system. Germany's Energiewende is another example of this future, though one that is potentially more democratic and more decentralised, than the previous example. Despite facilitating democratic processes and outcomes that have resulted in the establishment of citizen-orientated organisations like energy cooperatives, Germany has remained reluctant to pursue more significant transformations which would give greater power to its citizens over the energy system.

Democratic energy centralism characterises the top left-hand quadrant of the energy futures typology as shown in Figure 1. Democratic futures tend to be very hypothetical in nature as few examples exist that have been successfully implemented. The democratic energy centralism future comprises a centralised energy system operating within a society that controls political, economic and civil

institutions in a democratic fashion. In this scenario, a bureaucratic governance system would exist which could be held accountable by the general public, and decision-making would take place through democratic means. Large-scale renewable energy cooperatives through which generation, distribution and transmission systems are democratically controlled by consumers are an example of this type of future (M. J. Burke & Stephens, 2017). The democratic energy centralism future is distinguished from the technocratic energy centralism future by a political economy that promotes democratic, just and fair processes and outcomes regarding decisions on energy.

Lastly, democratic energy decentralism (bottom left-hand quadrant) shares many fundamental aspects of social organisation with democratic energy centralism, however the energy system comprises distributed energy technologies operating at decentralised levels whereby production and consumption occur close together. This future seeks to eliminate the view of energy as a commodity and allow all citizens access to energy. It reflects the ideal scenario envisioned by those working within the energy democracy literature who advocate for making energy a human right which individuals and communities have control over (Byrne *et al.*, 2009; Martinez, 2017; Seyfang *et al.*, 2013; van Veelen & van der Horst, 2018). This future seeks to eliminate the view of energy as a commodity and allow all citizens access to energy.

4.3 A just transition: toward a democratically (de)centralised energy future

Thombs (2019) argues that democratic energy futures are most compatible with a just energy transition that addresses matters of power, equity and social justice on top of environmental issues. The monopolistic characteristics of the technocratic energy centralism and libertarian energy decentralism futures, which undermine equity, fairness and recognition, are not compatible with the notion of a just transition. Democratic processes, he suggests, transcend capitalism and its unsustainable reliance on growth and expansion, surpassing the unequal social relations seen in capitalism that give rise to the exploitation of humans and the environment. Democratic energy centralism and democratic energy decentralism therefore remain the most appropriate energy futures to be pursued.

The most appropriate scale for the energy system will vary across contexts and favour certain characteristics of centralisation or decentralisation depending on different circumstances. These energy systems may either facilitate or hinder democratic and just processes and outcomes. Many scholars have argued that small-scale (decentralised) systems and technologies offer emerging opportunities for democratic processes and empowering social relationships that centralised systems do not allow for. Both complete decentralisation and centralisation of the energy system will create

barriers for democratic processes – a mix of scales remains the most foreseeable pathway to a future that is socially just and ecologically sustainable. Gui & MacGill, (2018) offer their own typology of future clean energy communities (CECs) which draws upon this narrative of centralisation and decentralisation and the importance of achieving a balance between the systems. In their typology the researchers categorise CEC's into three distinct structures or types – centralised, decentralised and distributed (illustrated in figure 2) – using examples from five Australian case studies, including the South Australia (SA) Virtual Power Plant (VPP), Western Australia (WA) Peer-to-Peer Trading trial and Hepburn wind community-scale energy projects.

Figure 2: Reproduction of Gui and MacGill's (2018, p100) proposed clean energy community network typology, delineated between centralised, distributed, and decentralised configurations.

Gui & MacGill (2018) characterise a centralised CEC as '*a cohesive network of households and businesses that collectively own or participate in energy-related projects, such as solar, wind and other clean energy generation projects, energy efficiency, demand-side management, community bulk-buying, etc.*'. Despite playing an important role in the clean energy transition, these centralised CECs can be integrated into the existing electricity infrastructure with relative ease, thus likely lacking the capacity to innovate and disrupt the existing large-scale centralised regime. Distributed CECs are defined by the researchers as '*a network of households and businesses that generate or own*

distributed generation individually, connected through a controlling entity either physically or virtually, and sharing the same rules in supplying and consuming electricity within the network' (Gui & MacGill, 2018). They are considered 'virtual' communities in that they are linked by an entity (like a technology provider or utility) but are not necessarily directly connected with each other geographically. Distributed CECs are heavily technology-infrastructure dependent and reliant on the centralised energy system. Lastly, decentralised CECs are defined as *'a community of households, businesses or a municipality that generates and consumes energy locally for self-sufficiency that may or may not connect to the main grid'*. These CECs remain self-sufficient and autonomous from the centralised energy system, with the energy resources – and sometimes the distribution infrastructure - being individually or collectively owned by members of a community who are geographically connected. In contrast to centralised CECs, decentralised energy projects will involve the deployment of new infrastructure and a reconfiguration of the existing energy infrastructure through long-term strategies and collective actions (Gui & MacGill, 2018).

The energy transition will be a slow and uncertain process involving the emergence of multiple technologies and innovations, rather than a breakthrough in one type of energy technology or social innovation (Geels & Schot, 2007). As communities differ in their goals and interests, problem definitions and interpretations, no one-size-fits-all model exists which can be applied to every scenario. As each CEC structure has its own strengths and weaknesses, appropriate technologies and business models must be cultivated based on the needs and desires of each specific community. Existing regime actors have the opportunity to act as 'facilitators' of change which they may adapt to and potentially gain advantages from, or as 'resistors' or 'blockers' of innovation and change in order to maintain their dominance in the energy system (Gui & MacGill, 2018) .

Figure 3 on page 24 features our interpretation of the current energy system, adapted from the work of Thombs (2019) and Gui and MacGill (2018). It places a number of common business models typically seen in the citizen energy arena in a position which appropriately conveys their individual contributions to the four potential energy futures described by Thombs (2019), drawing upon the typology outlined by Gui and MacGill (2018) in order to determine the vertical placement of these business models within the four quadrants. Gui and MacGill (2018) understand centralised citizen energy communities as energy-related projects that can be integrated into the existing large-scale electricity infrastructure with relative ease, remaining under the current centralised regime which is dominated by a small number of powerful utilities. These centralised systems require large-scale power stations and a 'national grid' infrastructure in order to distribute electricity to centres of demand. The majority of CECs observed in the literature could be considered examples of centralised energy projects in which community-scale renewable energy is pursued in various forms that

ultimately links back to the existing national grid network for distribution, for example, the Edinburgh Community Solar Co-operative in the UK. This is in opposition to energy projects which we consider to be completely 'decentralised' – off-grid systems which are disconnected from the national grid and thus creating almost an island-like effect of community energy supply, such as is the case in the Isle of Eigg, also in Scotland. This interpretation was taken into account in the creation of Figure 3 on the following page, where it was felt that CECs which are stereotypically perceived as decentralised systems – such as energy cooperatives – should be portrayed more accurately as ranging in position along the scale of centralised – decentralised technologies.

Energy cooperatives remain the most common and fastest-growing type of energy community initiative. Energy cooperatives are structured in order to benefit members of the cooperative itself, existing as social and economic enterprises that enable citizens to collectively own and manage energy projects (Yildiz *et al.*, 2015). Cooperatives are symbols of democratic governance, with decisions being made on the basis of the 'one member, one vote' principle. Cooperatives may act as decentralised systems, whereby energy generation and consumption occur close together, or may contribute towards the centralised energy system by feeding back into the national grid, despite the cooperative members reaping the benefits of membership. Housing associations (in this context) consist of non-profit associations offering benefits to tenants living in social housing with the aim of tackling energy poverty (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020). The energy system in this scenario may be centralised or decentralised, depending on whether the energy produced is first fed back into the national grid or used directly by tenants of the building. Housing associations vary as to their position on the democratic-monopolistic x-axis: as the tenants themselves may or may not be involved in the decision-making process, whether these business models are regarded as more democratic or monopolistic in nature really depends on each specific scenario. Limited partnerships represent another form of citizen participation in the energy sector, usually characterised as an agreement between a limited liability company, acting as a general partner, and citizens, acting as limited partners (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020). Limited partnerships are common among larger projects requiring high levels of investment, which influences the governance structure of the agreement – the voting rights of a limited partnership are usually proportional to the value of each partner's share, or the amount of capital invested. Understandably, therefore, citizens will tend to have less influence over the decision-making process than the general partner, who has often invested the greater amount in the project and so has a greater level of control. Limited partnerships may therefore take a number of positions along on the democratic-monopolistic axis, again depending on the specific situation, though usually will fall on the more monopolistic side. As these projects are usually quite large, the system in this scenario could generally be considered more

Figure 3: Our interpretation of the current energy system, adapted from the work of both Thombs (2019) and Gui and MacGill (2018)

centralised than decentralised in that the energy produced may feed back into the national grid and though citizen shareholders may benefit from ownership in the project they do not directly consumer the energy produced. Public-private partnerships involve agreements between local authorities and citizen groups and businesses which aim to ensure the provision of benefits for a community (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020). In this scenario the energy system typically remains centralised, contributing towards the existing energy system, though depending on the level of consumer engagement in the process voting rights may prove either more democratic or monopolistic. Public utility companies are run by municipalities and provide a representation of the current technocratic energy centralism future typically seen today. These companies contribute towards the existing centralised energy system in which a few key players hold the majority of influence and decision-making power, and citizens have less opportunity to participate.

4.4 Stakeholder Participation in Company Decision-Making

Public participation in company processes is now considered by some an essential ingredient for the long-term success of a business, which has been highlighted by both national and international conventions, such as Agenda 21. Public participation has become a topic of serious debate for modern companies, who have come to recognise the benefits associated with meeting the expectations of the public regarding a number of issues, which may only occur when public concerns are appropriately identified and addressed. However, despite gaining broad acceptance over the years, stakeholder participation in companies continues to be limited to marketing and consumer engagement regarding product functioning and rarely is it seen that a company uses ongoing participatory measures within their business processes. Instead, stakeholder participation appears to be more commonly employed on an ad hoc basis when resolving conflicts and its use may present more as a means of informing decisions rather than helping to make decisions (Oxley Green & Hunton-Clarke, 2003). Monitoring and understanding the continuously evolving concerns of citizens is necessary to proactively address issues and meet the expectations of the public (Zadek *et al.*, 2013), which can provide many opportunities and benefits to the decision-making process, both from the information gained by participation and through the process itself.

Given its potential significance, Oxley Green and Hunton-Clarke (2003) proposed a typology of stakeholder participation for company decision-making which offers a more structured and systematic approach to stakeholder participation in the company context, based on an analysis of its roots within the public sector. The typology proposed by Oxley Green & Hunton-Clarke (2003) builds upon the spectrum of involvement proposed by Dorcey *et al.* (1994, as cited in Jackson 2001), which ranges from 'inform' and 'educate' through to 'consensus seeking' and 'ongoing involvement'.

4.5 A Company Perspective Towards Participation

'Community' focused typologies provide several key elements that can be applied to develop a 'company' focused typology that is simple to understand and relatable to a variety of company situations and decision-making processes. Oxley Green and Hunton-Clarke (2003) identify three key levels of participation for application to various business models: *informative*, *consultative* and *decisional*.

1. Informative participation refers to the process by which information is passed from one body to another, such as advertising used to inform the public of future plans. The role of the stakeholder at this level is simply to receive information, and participation remains passive, with the company holding complete control over the manner in which stakeholders are informed and what information they receive. Sometimes informative participation can involve a two-way dialogue, such as through the use of surveys, though participation is limited in this scenario which doesn't explore stakeholders' understanding, values and attitudes and doesn't lead to further dialogue.
2. Consultative participation describes a higher level of public participation whereby stakeholders are allowed to offer their views and perspectives on certain company matters at a more exploratory level than with the previous example. Qualitative research methods may be used to explore citizens' attitudes and values, and the information generated may potentially be used to influence the decision-making process. Consultative participation limits the extent to which citizens can influence the decision-making process, as decisions may have already been made, however involving stakeholders in the process can still result in solutions that are more widely accepted by stakeholders.
3. Decisional participation refers to the level at which stakeholders actually get to participate in the decision-making process, whereby stakeholders are invited by organisations to participate in the project process from the very beginning. The process of fully engaging stakeholder groups in the decision-making process requires significant commitment from a company, but these actions can lead to the sharing of views and knowledge and reconciliation of contrasting goals and objectives at an earlier stage in the process. The decisions arising from the process of decisional participation are likely to be more socially acceptable to stakeholder groups and lead to greater long-term success.

The type of participation that should be used will depend on the situation or problem at hand, as well as the degree of commitment by the business and what they expect from the process. They will each

generate different outcomes and involve various ‘risks’, making different degrees of participation more or less appropriate for different types of decision-making. Oxley Green and Hunton-Clarke (2003) go on to describe the possible modes of stakeholder engagement with companies by combining the levels of participation described in their typology with the different frequencies, or purposes, of participation, see Figure 4 below.

Figure 4: Modes of stakeholder participation as described by Oxley Green and Hunton-Clarke (2003).

The researchers propose that in order for companies to fully involve stakeholders in the decision-making process and activities, a shift must take place towards more decisional and ongoing participation processes, which offers different benefits, and requires and portrays different levels of commitment to stakeholders, than *ad hoc* participation. Ongoing participation offers companies the chance to obtain deeper insights into the values and attitudes of stakeholders, however *ad hoc* processes will also be required for help in resolving specific issues and, if built upon a strong foundation of ongoing and committed stakeholder participation, shouldn't be seen by citizens as token gestures to appease stakeholders, as they have been seen in the past.

The typology reveals a significant graduation from *informative* to *decisional* participation, as informing decisions at the consultative level doesn't result in changes to the decision-making process, which may be kept separate from the stakeholder participation process. Advancing beyond the informative and consultative levels can be a source of apprehension for companies due to the lack of standard methodologies and guidelines, as the risks involved in getting it wrong, as well as the required financial and time resources, remain clear. Greater stakeholder involvement within company decision-making

requires a form of *decisional* participation which could potentially result in more sustainable decisions (Acland, 2000), though may not be appropriate for companies who are not open to changes being made to their decision-making processes and who are apprehensive at the prospect of relinquishing control (Wilcox, 1994). Decisional participatory processes wouldn't necessarily result in the same decisions being made as would occur if stakeholders were not allowed to participate, and thus they call for changes to be made to the traditional ways that many companies work. A standard model for stakeholder participation is required in order to encourage companies to take the necessary steps towards decisional participation.

5 Conclusion

This report '*Typology of citizen participation*', continues and concludes the work reported in initial deliverables: '*Report on citizen participation at the macro level*' and '*Description of emergent governance & organisational frameworks*', which provided the foundation in consumerist, civic and communitarian forms of participation necessary to explore the various ways that citizens engage with the energy system and how their actions are conditioned by current and emerging governance structures. Drawing from Thombs (2019) and Gui and MacGill (2018), this report featured a typology to represent the current energy system, placing a number of common business models that are typically seen in the citizen energy arena to convey their individual contributions to potential energy futures. These are located between a social scale with a spectrum of democratic to monopolistic, and with an energy system scale, on a spectrum of centralised to decentralised. The typology sees potential energy futures fall into four broad quadrants of a 2 x 2 matrix which includes libertarian energy decentralism, technocratic energy centralism, democratic energy centralism, and democratic energy decentralism. The deliverable finally argues that democratic futures, either central or not, are the most compatible with a just energy transition that looks at matters of power, equity and social justice.

The deliverable finally introduces a typology of stakeholder participation that identifies three key levels of participation in business models. Informative participation which refers to the process in which information is passed from one body to another, consultative participation where stakeholders are allowed to offer their views and perspectives, and decisional participation where stakeholders get to participate in the decision-making process. The report concludes that the type of participation that is to be used will depend on the situation or problem at hand, and the degree of commitment by businesses in the process. Taken together, These three outputs from WP1 provide a good base for the work in WP2 that will focus on mapping stakeholders, their connection to the project, and their relation to the various governance and organisational frameworks conditioning their participation.

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